

MultiXscale

Guidelines for Community Outreach, Education, and Training

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides guidelines for how to design, organise, and record the delivery of training material related to MultiXscale.

We outline lesson design principles that should be considered when creating training content:

- Use *reverse design*, where you decide lesson objectives and assessments that would constitute evidence that the objectives have been met. You then work backwards, sorting your assessments and designing your lesson to teach towards each assessment.
- Good *learning objectives* are quite specific about the intended effect of a lesson on its learners. We aim to create learning objectives that are specific, accurate, and informative for both learners and instructors.
- Good exercises are the most important factor in a good lesson. Well designed *formative assessment* tasks – i.e. quick questions and exercises – can go a long way towards correcting misconceptions and expanding the mental models of learners.

We provide guidance on two template format that can be used, [the Carpentries Workbench](#) and [MkDocs](#). Both templates allow for implementation of the same development best practices for training content that are already being used by project participants for their software development, including code review and CI/CD.

Training components are considered at three different proficiency levels:

- Awareness, where a presentation is considered the appropriate medium;
- Working knowledge, where a tutorial with hands-on components are appropriate;
- Specialist knowledge, where a dedicated workshop is required.

Given that technical training components of MultiXscale are largely targeted at the user community of European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI), here we only consider training at the awareness or working knowledge level. Such training components may attract a large and varied audience, and can primarily be given in an online format.

If specialist knowledge technical or scientific training is being provided, then a specific event can be considered in cases where such specialised training is not already provided elsewhere, or where there is particularly high demand within the community for tailored content. Such events are expected to target a specific audience, and as such as well suited to in-person and hybrid formats. For the scientific training components of MultiXscale, scientific partners are expected to apply for funding via the events program of Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire (CECAM).

We outline what should be done in the three months preceding a training event, such as defining the event content and program, defining the software and HPC requirements, etc. We also provide specific guidelines for in-person, online, and hybrid format training events.

MultiXscale is creating it's own *Ambassador Program*. It is conceived as a train-the-trainers program where we cultivate and support MultiXscale representation within the nodal structure of eligible countries of CECAM and at the NCC of EuroHPC participant countries, using it as a scalable model for initial outreach and support for MultiXscale activities. Training courses with high expected interest (i.e., capacity-oriented courses, most likely domain independent) will be held in hybrid modes, with remote instruction and local support by members of our Ambassador Program. All content will be available online and reusable with a liberal licence. MultiXscale also collaborates with projects [CASTIEL2](#) and [BioNT](#) on specific training initiatives.

The training program is supported by technical infrastructure:

- Hosting for collaborative note-taking is done via [HackMD](#),
- [Magic Castle](#) is used to replicate the HPC infrastructure experience via community or commercial cloud resources,
- [Lhumos](#) is a web portal for educational material for modelling and simulation which is used to host the recorded material and any associated content (Git repositories, PDFs, etc.).

1 Introduction

The training content to be delivered reflects the structure of MultiXscale, with scientific and technical components.

The scientific components are geared towards the multiscale domain and expected to be a deep dive into some specific aspect related to the scientific showcases, catering to a relatively small and specific audience. Such training events are likely to make up the vast majority of MultiXscale in-person training events. Given that all scientific partners are members of CECAM, these events will also likely feature in the [CECAM program](#).

The technical aspects of MultiXscale cover software usage, software distribution, scaling, and portability, as well as other aspects such as Continuous Integration and/or Continuous Deployment (CI/CD). Since such content is largely domain-independent, it has a wider potential audience and is well suited for online delivery and content reuse.

The deliverable offers lesson design principles (Section 2), templates (Section 2.2), organisational guidelines (Section 3), and technical infrastructure (Section 4) to support the design, collaborative development, delivery, and archival of training content. It also outlines some of the training collaborations (Section 3.3) that we are currently engaged in.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable is intended to serve as a guide for those creating and delivering training content in the context of MultiXscale. It provides guidelines on designing training content, as well as detailing the technical infrastructure that can assist lesson development and lesson delivery.

It also includes an initial summary of the types of training that will be carried out by the project with initial estimates of when these trainings will take place.

1.2 Target audience

The recommendations of this report are intended for all contributors to the training component of the MultiXscale project. For a wider audience, it provides an outline of the training content that MultiXscale will provide and the technical infrastructure that will be used to support it.

2 Designing Training Content

2.1 Lesson Design Principles

The guiding principles recommended by MultiXscale are based on those provided by [The Carpentries](#) [1]. That guide is quite extensive though, so we refer instead to the material derived from this by [CodeRefinery](#) for [Lesson Design](#) that are delivered during their [instructor training course](#). From this we reproduce some particular material below.

2.1.1 Reverse Design

When creating training content for MultiXscale, we recommend taking a "reverse" approach to instruction, as described in Wiggins and McTighe's *Understanding by Design* [2], that keeps the focus firmly on learning outcomes. The order of preparation in this case becomes

- Determine your learning objectives.
- Decide what constitutes evidence that objectives have been met, and design assessments to target that evidence.
- Design instruction: Sort assessments in order of increasing complexity, and write content that connects everything together.

2.1.2 Learning Objectives

Figure 1: How to decide what you should teach in a lesson

The Carpentries have created a helpful visual guide to assist you in deciding what you should be teaching during your lesson, see Figure 1.

It is recommended that your lessons have learning objectives associated with them. Good learning objectives are quite specific about the intended effect of a lesson on its learners. We aim to create learning objectives that are specific, accurate, and informative for both learners and instructors.

In practice, it's best to start defining your target audience by answering to questions such as:

- What is the expected educational or skill level of my audience?
- Have they been already exposed to the technologies I am planning to teach?
- What tools do they already use?
- What are the main issues they are currently experiencing?

Once you clarified your target audience, it is useful to create learner personas. This will help you during the development process by providing concrete examples of potential learners showing up at your workshops.

- For each learner persona, try to think of what is useful to them.
- What do they need to remember/understand/apply?
- Then, you create a sequence of exercises which test incrementally progressing tasks and acquisition of the new skills.
- Finally, you write material to teach the gap between exercises.

2.1.3 Designing formative assessment

Well designed formative assessment tasks – i.e. quick questions and exercises – can go a long way towards correcting misconceptions and expanding the mental models of learners.

Some suggestions to keep in mind when designing exercises include:

- Not every exercise has to be an amazing hand-on example. Mixing with smaller, more conceptual things can reduce cognitive load.
- Try to make your exercises relevant, meaningful, and connected to previous knowledge. Connect the exercises to the real world. When learners understand the meaning of new concepts it will be easier for them to remember.
- Create more involved exercises that can be optional for more advanced learners. This is a way to meet the needs of participants with a wide range of background knowledge.

Good exercises are the most important factor in a good lesson. Even if you are preparing the rest of the lesson mostly alone, consider a good long brainstorming session to go from "list of topics to cover" to "sequence of exercises".

When you are stuck thinking "how can I make an exercise that covers X", look through the lists below for inspiration. Not every exercise has to be an sophisticated hands-on thing, so don't be afraid to use different types.

Types of exercises:

- Multiple choice (easy to get feedback via a classroom tool; try to design each wrong answer so that it identifies a specific misconception).
- Code yourself (traditional programming).
- Code yourself + multiple choice to see what the answer is (allows you to get feedback).
- Minimal fix (given broken code, make it work).
- Parsons problems (working solution but lines in random order, learner must "only" put them in proper order).
- Fill in the blank, faded problems.
- Tracing execution.
- Tracing values through code flow.
- Reverse execution (find input that gives an output).
- Theme and variations (working code, adapt to other type of situation/problem).
- Refactoring.
- Draw a diagram.
- Label diagram.
- Matching problem: two sets of questions and answers, match them.

2.2 Suggested Templates

2.2.1 The Carpentries Lesson Template

The Carpentries have created lesson development infrastructure, called the Carpentries Workbench to make it easier for instructors to follow these design. They have created a [lesson on how to leverage the Carpentries Workbench](#) and, given that it has been created specifically to support lesson development, this is the main recommendation for a template for MultiXscale lesson content.

2.2.2 Linking Documentation and Tutorial(s)

[EasyBuild](#) has found it very helpful to have some synchronisation and cross-referencing between the project documentation (which is typically quite technical given that it is reference documentation) and the [EasyBuild Tutorial](#) about the project (which is targeted mostly towards new users). Since the parties generating material for both use cases overlap, it is very helpful to use the same format for both. In the case of EasyBuild, the underlying platform is [MkDocs](#). The reference documentation and tutorial are both repositories within the [EasyBuilders GitHub organisation](#), and are subject to the same code review practices as all the software EasyBuild produces.

3 Organisational Guidelines

Training components are considered at three different proficiency levels:

- Awareness, where a presentation is considered the appropriate medium;
- Working knowledge, where a tutorial with hands-on components are appropriate;
- Specialist knowledge, where a dedicated workshop is required.

Given that technical training components of MultiXscale are largely targeted at the user community of EESSI, here we only consider training at the awareness or working knowledge level. Such training components may attract a large and varied audience and can primarily be given in an online format.

If specialist knowledge technical or scientific training is being provided, then a specific event can be considered in cases where such specialised training is not already provided elsewhere or where there is particularly high demand within the community for tailored content. Such events are expected to target a specific audience, and as such as well suited to in-person and hybrid formats.

For the scientific training components of MultiXscale, scientific partners are expected to apply for funding via the events program of CECAM.

3.1 Preparing for a Training Event

We have attempted to build a timeline that the event organizers and co-organisers should follow to achieve a successfully training event:

- Before the workshop
 - 3 months before
 1. Define event content.
 2. Build up an initial event program.
 3. Evaluate the need for additional technical training, either developed as part of the event itself or organized by another training organization (e.g. Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE)) and leveraged by the event.
 - 2 months before
 1. Discuss software requirements and applications that will be used with the Technical Manager.
 2. If required, discuss also the need for High Performance Computing (HPC) resources.
 - 1 month before
 1. Define training material to be added to the MultiXscale training platform, and (where appropriate) an assessment form to evaluate software and application skills before the event
 2. Outline the lectures that should be recorded
 3. Prepare setup to allow for remote participation (if applicable)
- At the workshop
 - At least one person from the relevant MultiXscale Work Package (WP) should attend the meeting to provide (at a minimum) any necessary technical support
 - Record the lectures (audio/video with slides) as defined in advance of the meeting
- After the workshop
 - Gather responses to the workshop survey
 - Produce a short event report

3.2 Training Delivery Formats

There are many qualities that can make a good teacher such as patience and leadership, but teaching in and of itself is a skill and can be learned. There is extensive research into teaching methodologies but unfortunately most project participants are unlikely to have the available time to leverage them. We are lucky that through our collaboration with

CASTIEL2 (see Section 3.3.2), we have access to instructor training courses (such as [Best Practices in HPC training](#) organised by ENCCS and held in September 2023).

3.2.1 In Person Delivery

Carefully reviewing the content of your workshop is important. However, it is common for instructors to over-prepare on technical content and under-prepare the learner-centered elements of their teaching. If you encounter questions that you can't answer, demonstrating how you navigate your way to a solution may earn surprisingly positive feedback. In contrast, neglecting to attend to the audience usually has much more serious consequences for learning and morale.

One of the cornerstones of The Carpentries teaching is live coding: instructors do not use slides to teach coding, but work through the lesson material, typing in the code or instructions, with the workshop participants following along. They have given a list of [Top Ten Tips for Participatory Live Coding in a Workshop](#):

1. Stand up and move around the room if possible.
2. Go slowly. For every command you type, every word of code you write, every menu item or website button you click, say out loud what you are doing while you do it. Then point to the command and its output on the screen and go through it a second time. This slows you down and allows learners to copy what you do, or to catch up. Do not copy-paste code.
3. Mirror your learners' environment. Avoid using keyboard shortcuts.
4. Use your screen wisely. Use a big font, and maximize the window. A black font on a white background works better than a light font on a dark background.
5. Use illustrations to help learners understand and organize the material. It helps learners understand the material, makes for a more lively workshop and gathers the learners' attention to you as well.
6. Turn off notifications on your laptop and phone.
7. Stick to the lesson material. It may be tempting to deviate from the material because you would like to show a neat trick, or demonstrate some alternative way of doing something. Do not do this, since there is a fair chance you will run into something unexpected that you then have to explain.
8. Leave no learner behind.
9. Embrace mistakes. No matter how well prepared you are, you will make mistakes. Use these opportunities to do error framing and to help your learners learn the art of troubleshooting.
10. Have fun: It is OK to use humor and improvisation to liven up the workshop. This becomes easier when you are more familiar with the material, and more relaxed. Start small, even just saying 'that was fun' after something worked well is a good start.

Know your audience, create a profile for a learner in your workshop. Critically analyze a learning objective for your workshop. Identify checkpoints in a lesson for formative assessment.

3.2.2 Online Delivery

Guidelines for online learning are derived from [The Carpentries Online Workshop Recommendations](#).

Teaching online is a challenge. The recommendations are focused on the leanest possible technology using systems we are already familiar with. While many other options exist and will likely make their way into our guidelines (e.g. additional tools, semi-synchronous approaches), we currently recommend procedures that are as close as possible to standard practices for live instruction.

Learning online is also a challenge. The most common barriers for learners are likely to be unreliable internet connections and the limitation of a small single screen. Instructors and learners should anticipate these problems.

Software installation is a challenge regardless of format, and issue resolution during an event is even more problematic online. We strongly recommend pre-workshop support with software installation.

Many online workshops move more slowly than in-person events, and require more detailed planning:

- Think about time
 - Choose a time format: 2 full days or...?
 - Identify time zones: where is everyone?

- Identify the number of learners
- Plan time to teach learners how to participate
- Plan time for breaks and socialisation
- Plan time for exercises and transitions
- Choose content to cut as the need arises
- Choose your technology
 - Choose a conferencing platform
 - Choose chat and collaborative document platforms
- Plan for instruction
 - Who teaches what?
 - Who plays what role(s) during the workshop?
 - Software installation
 - Teaching learners how to participate
 - Check-ins and exercises
 - Social/collaborative opportunities
 - Accessibility
 - Emergency planning
 - Set up for feedback collection
 - Instructional team meetings
 - Workshop follow-up

3.2.3 Hybrid Delivery

Hybrid brings together the worst of both worlds. You need to take into account all the needs of both formats, and cater to two audiences simultaneously. The reality is, you simply cannot do this alone. You can be the primary instructor in a single room but you are going to need helpers in the room with you, and you are going to need helpers to assist with your online participants.

MultiXscale aims to create an Ambassador Program (see Section 3.3.1) where we have remote instructors and participants in a number of local classrooms. This increases further the active participation (and importance) of the helpers in the remote classrooms.

3.3 Collaborations with Other Initiatives

3.3.1 The MultiXscale Ambassador Program

The MultiXscale Ambassador Program is conceived as a train-the-trainers program where we cultivate and support MultiXscale representation within the nodal structure of eligible countries of CECAM and at the National Competence Centre (NCC) of EuroHPC participant countries, using it as a scalable model for initial outreach and support for MultiXscale activities.

Training courses with high expected interest (i.e., capacity-oriented courses, most likely domain independent) will be held in hybrid modes, with remote instruction and local support by members of our Ambassador Program. All content will be available online and reusable with a liberal licence.

3.3.2 CASTIEL2

MultiXscale has a collaboration agreement with CASTIEL2, and as part of this agreement will carry out a number of collaborations in the training space.

At this stage of the project, we emphasize the importance of the "Train the Trainers" event that has been coordinated by CASTIEL2 and will hopefully be held again in the future. This is of high value to MultiXscale as it can act as a synchronisation point for the Ambassador Program (of Section 3.3.1), and provide a level base (and prerequisite) across ambassadors when it comes the scope and delivery of the ambassador program content.

3.3.3 BioNT

BioNT is an international consortium of nine partners, including six academic entities and three Small and Medium enterprises (SMEs). The vision of the consortium is to provide a high-quality training program and community for digital skills relevant to the biotechnology industry and biomedical sector.

There is some overlap of partners and some training themes between the two projects that have created opportunities to develop specific introductory HPC oriented training content.

4 Technical Infrastructure

4.1 Lesson Development

4.1.1 Lesson formatting and shared note-taking

[Markdown](#) is a commonly used mark-up language that is used with plain text to add formatting elements (headings, bulleted lists, URLs) to plain text without the use of a formal text editor or the use of HTML tags. This makes it well suited for use with Git source code repositories, and it is supported out-of-the-box by repository hosting platforms such as GitHub and GitLab.

In Section 2.2, we referenced two platforms that support Markdown. Given the ubiquity of Markdown and our choice of templates, we choose to maintain the use of Markdown also in the note-taking that takes place during our training events. This approach means that attendees are also implicitly exposed to the tools they need to also (hopefully) contribute to the lesson they are being taught. The platform we use for hosting the shared note-taking is [HackMD](#).

4.1.2 CI/CD

Both of the suggested templates of Section 2.2 use GitHub Actions for their continuous integration workflows, and for their lesson deployment. Maintaining both this aspects on a single platform is of high value, and a great simplification to lesson development.

4.2 Compute Resources for Training Events

To give additional flexibility and allow us to streamline our workflow we use replicate HPC clusters in cloud computing resources so that we can offer resources to learners for our training events.

4.2.1 Magic Castle

[Magic Castle](#) is an open-source software that replicates the HPC infrastructure experience via community or commercial cloud resources. It is easy to deploy and can be created in minutes. Once their cluster is deployed, the user is provided with a complete HPC cluster software environment including the scheduler, a data-transfer node, JupyterHub, and thousands of software applications compiled by experts and accessible via CernVM-FS. Since its initial public release in 2018, Magic Castle has been used for thousands of workshops and tutorials world-wide.

Magic Castle uses the open-source software [Terraform](#) to define the virtual machines, volumes, and networks that are required to replicate a virtual HPC infrastructure. The infrastructure definition is packaged as a Terraform module that users can customize as they require. After deployment, the user is provided with a complete HPC cluster software environment including a Slurm scheduler, a Globus Endpoint, JupyterHub, LDAP, DNS, and research software applications compiled by experts via EESSI. Magic Castle is compatible with AWS, Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, OpenStack, and OVH.

4.3 Archiving of Training Events

Only some of the training content produced by MultiXscale will be repeated over the lifetime of the project. Therefore, it is important that we take the opportunity to record the tutorial content we deliver as much as possible and make it available to learners outside of the tutorial environment.

4.3.1 The Lhumos Training Portal

Figure 2: Lhumos display of presentation capture with associated GitHub repository.

Learning Hub For Modelling and Simulation (*Lhumos*) is a web portal for educational material for modelling and simulation. It is being co-developed by MultiXscale, after being designed, conceived, and implemented within the MultiXscale predecessor E-CAM.

The portal is built using [Clowder](#), a scalable data repository where you can share, organize, and analyze data. Clowder is a data repository that you can instruct on how to process and present the data it consumes. For a new data type (such as a captured presentation in our case) you need to do this by the creation of an *extractor* to process the data as you wish, and a *previewer* to present it. The extractor can include the creation of additional metadata and files to feed into your previewer.

The logical structure of Clowder can be easily leveraged for training purposes. Single files are collected into *datasets*, which are a group of files that through some defined relationship or corresponding metadata are strongly tied together and not representable otherwise by the individual files. Datasets are what we expect our captured lectures to be (made up of the associated videos, lecture materials, reading materials, tutorial content and software requirements). *Collections* are a user defined group of datasets and other collections. A space is a group of collections, datasets, and files with defined user access rights. Spaces are used to share data within datasets and collections with other users, in our case this will be how we will restrict access to (some of) our material.

Clowder is intended to help support the training aspects of future or ongoing events and to build a repository of training/background material by integrating new material from those events. It also allows contributors to the repository to disseminate their training/expository material more widely for constructive use in future events.

Since E-CAM, the original Clowder instance is now being giving a far more user-friendly interface by *CECAM*, called *Lhumos*, while still retaining the original Clowder framework for data storage and metadata generation (see Figure 2).

MultiXscale has extended Clowder to allow metadata extraction for

- YouTube videos,
- GitHub and GitLab repositories,
- Generating high quality previews of PDF documents,
- Exposing the contents of ZIP archives.

5 Conclusions

The guidelines contained in this deliverable cover both the scientific and technical aspects of MultiXscale. The project is aware that the nature of training in each aspect is quite different. As such we advise that partners follow the guidelines to the extent that the effort required to do so is of high enough future value.

Specifically, we suggest that training content that is unlikely to be re-used in the future (or by another party) does not necessarily have to follow the templates of Section 2.2, since implementing these comes with non-negligible effort. Nevertheless, all content should try to follow the lesson design principles of Section 2.1, and content delivery should be captured and placed on the MultiXscale section of the Lhumos Training Portal (see Section 4.3.1).

References

Acronyms Used

HPC High Performance Computing
CECAM Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire
WP Work Package
EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
CI/CD Continuous Integration and/or Continuous Deployment
NCC National Competence Centre
Lhumos Learning Hub For Modelling and Simulation

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